

Introduction to Engineering Design

Chapter 3

Communication and Collaboration in Multi-Disciplinary Teams

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Learning Objectives to be achieved:

1. To identify the importance of communication in project success
2. To determine the characteristics of a good collaborator
3. To recognize the abilities of an excellent multi-disciplinary team
4. To determine how to maintain an effective team that will contribute to the proposed Engineering Design project to address any of the Sustainable Development Goals.

3.0 Introduction

In the first week's discussion, the challenge to take part in the Sustainable Development Goals action using the Greening Engineering Framework (GEF) that served as a theme to the Engineering Design Challenge 2022 was taken on board as an engineering design team was discussed and organized in the second week.

This third week, the discussion of how communication and collaboration tum's team's success even in a diverse team membership or multi-disciplinary nature.

This third week's topics respond to the second-course objective: "On completion of this subject, the students can participate within and contribute to a multi-discipline engineering design team through the application of team roles and communication".

The week two lecture discusses the Engineering Design team and its roles. A team is a **small** number of persons that has a **complementary skills** committed to a **same purpose**, and **performance goals** and **approach** holding themselves **accountable** (PocketbookWisdom of Teams). The success of the team's work is teamwork. *Teamwork* is the fuel for ordinary people to achieve uncommon results, says Einstein, and Effective teams are willing to help others who are less effective (Lucas).

Figure 15. Teamwork Triangle. Adapted from (PocketbookWisdom of Teams)

Teamwork **Enhances Learning process**

- Teamwork creates opportunity for collaborative learning.
- Motivation keeps the Teamwork vibrant.
- Persons (students, engineering colleagues) are the best motivators of other people.
- Teaching others is the most profound method of learning.
- Solution process is speed up in Teamwork
- How engineering professionals work and learn.

Teams outperform individuals acting alone or in larger organizational groupings, especially when performance requires multiple skills, judgments, and experiences.'

3.1 Importance of Communication for a Design Project success

3.1.1 Importance of project communication in the design project success is

- ✓ that communication delivers the information to the project team and its stakeholder
- ✓ determines who will be receiving the communication
- ✓ how those people will receive it
- ✓ when they will receive it
- ✓ how often should they expect to receive that information
- ✓ it drives the momentum of the project
- ✓ keep the hard deadline at the forefront of your team's mind

3.1.2 Communication processes

Figure 16. Communication scheme

3.1.2.1 Information

- A. Idea formation- information of the idea is to be communicated simply for understanding. The information must contain the basic information: What, Where, When, Why, How
- B. Delivery of message-

B.1 verbal

- a. Traditional-In person (face to-face)
- b. Technology (online, internet, apps (Messenger, WhatsApp, zoom, team, etc)

B.2 Non-verbal

B.2.1 written

- a. Traditional (report, article, letter, memo)
- b. Technology (apps, blogs, email, google

B.2.2 visual

- Traditional- body language, facial expression, photos
- Technology

3.1.2.4 Listening

Translate the message

3.1.2.4 Message

- Embodied the idea and how this idea can be executed

3.1.2.4 Action (execution)

- Feedback (response)
- Project Goal setting
- Project Planning
 - *Poor communication contributes to project failure that leads to great financial loss
 - * High-performing businesses communicate more frequently and do more effectively
 - * Keep the project on track due to it:
 - Creates written documentation that the team can reference
 - Sets expectations of when stakeholders will receive updates
 - Increases stakeholders' visibility of the project and its status
 - It provides the opportunity for stakeholders to give feedback, which can help the team detect issues early on and decrease wasted work
 - Increases productivity during meetings or eliminates them altogether

How to make a project communication plan

1. Choose a format – word document, spreadsheet, google sheets, google doc, google slide, template, flowchart
2. Choose a platform – easy to gather feedback, share the information, store information for future reference, google drive
3. Choose a communication goal
 - Pen the team's goal
 - *Update stakeholders on the project status
 - *Keep stakeholders mindful of the project's benefit's so they will continue to advocate for it
 - Set how often it is done (weekly, fortnightly, monthly, etc.)
4. Identify stakeholders
 - *Most projects have many stakeholders
 - *Most of whom have different levels of interest in and influence on the project
 - *Identify stakeholders with whom you'll communicate throughout the project and list them
5. Identify communication methods:
 - weekly check-in
 - meetings, whether in person, over the phone or through video conferencing
 - meeting minutes
 - status reports
 - formal presentations
 - surveys
 - to-do lists
 - project dashboards
 - collaboration apps, such as Slack, and Google apps
 - the communication method you choose may also depend on the information you need to deliver
 - example, in-person meetings weekly to share updates on the project, send a weekly email with updates, holding meetings when the team reaches a major milestone
6. Determine the frequency of communication
 - List how often communication is sent.

Example: send a weekly email every Monday with project progress, links to completed deliverables, current budget, etc.)

- Schedule communication frequency on your calendar

7. Determine who provides the communication updates

*Project leader

*Task leader

8. Flexibility when project changes

*No business is immune to scope creep, even the best-organized companies will face times when project change- need to change the project plan

* Refer to your project overview and realign your communication plan to the revised project.

* Communication plan act as your North Star when the problem starts to arise

9. Avoid too much detail often

10. standardized the process

11. Avoid barriers in communication

- Conflict
- Unmet goals
- Lost friendship

Meetings

●A project kick-off meeting is the best opportunity for a project manager or team leader to energize the team.

●The project management or team plan can establish a common goal and start understanding each individual through a meeting.

●Although a project kick-off meeting appears to be a simple meeting with all the stakeholders of the project, a successful project kick-off meeting requires proper planning.

Kick-off Meetings usually include the following:

3. Introduction

2. Project Briefing

a. Purpose of the project

b. Project goals

c. Business problem

d. Project scope

3. Kick-off Meeting

- Objectives, Project Scope & Schedule
- Teams Roles & Responsibilities
- Procedural Requirements
- Project Administration requirements
- Periodic or 60-90 day key plan and action

Regular Meeting

Agenda & Minutes Sample Format (Adapted from NYU's Office of Learning and Organizational Development at 212-998-1250.)

MEETING AGENDA

Meeting/Project Name:			
Date of Meeting: (MM/DD/YYYY)		Time:	
Meeting Facilitator:		Location:	

1. Meeting Objective			

2. Attendees			
Name	Department/Division	E-mail	Phone

3. Meeting Agenda		
Topic	Owner	Time

4. Pre-work/Preparation (documents/handouts to bring, reading material, etc.)	
Description	Prepared by

Figure 17 Agenda Template

MEETING MINUTES

Meeting/Project Name:			
Date of Meeting: (MM/DD/YYYY)		Time:	
Minutes Prepared By:		Location:	
1. Meeting Objective			
2. Attendance at Meeting			
Name	Department/Division	Email	Phone
3. Agenda and Notes, Decisions, Issues			
Topic		Owner	Time
4. Action Items			
Action		Owner	Due Date
5. Next Meeting (if applicable)			
Date: (MM/DD/YYYY)		Time:	
		Location:	
Objective:			

Figure 18 Agenda Template

Collaboration in Engineering

3.2 Design team?

- **A key element of Good team collaboration** (Key features of (good) team collaboration)
 - ✓ A small number of people
 - ✓ Complimentary skills
 - ✓ Common purpose
 - ✓ Performance goals
 - ✓ Approach
 - ✓ Mutual accountability
- **Qualities of a great collaborator** (Hymes)
 - ✓ *Egoless*, more interested in helping everyone achieve the mutual goal than personally getting credit.
 - ✓ *generous*, able to share knowledge, skills, help, and encouragement or any need of the team with joy
 - ✓ curious,
 - ✓ *appreciative*, express sincere appreciation and thanks, and give a credit where credit is due
 - ✓ *listen to understand*,
 - ✓ *flexible*, go with the flow, bending with the wind helps them survive the storm
 - ✓ *willingness to connect*
 - ✓ *give and expect trust*
 - ✓ *discipline*
 - ✓ *self-motivated*
 - ✓ *respectful*

3.3 Multi-disciplinary Team

- Civil Engineering – that deals with the design, construction, and maintenance of the physical and naturally built environment (sub-discipline: coastal, construction, earthquake, forensic, geotechnical, material science, surveying, municipal or urban, water resource, civil engineering systems), is the application of physical and scientific principles for solving the problems of society.
- Electrical Engineering – concerned with the use of electricity, electronics, and electromagnetis,design, study and application of equipment, devices and systems.
- Mechanical Engineering – combines engineering physics and mathematics principles to design, analyze, manufacture, and maintain mechanical systems.
- Mining Engineering – extraction of minerals from underneath, above or on the ground
- Mineral Processing – field of extractive metallurgy, also known as ore dressing, separates commercially valuable minerals from the ores.

The Design Engineer & Collaborator

- Design engineers may work in a team to create the drawings necessary for prototyping and production with other designers. But, with the advent of CAD and solid modelling software, design engineers may create the drawings or perhaps may require the help of other corporate service providers.
 - ✓ Resolving Any Conflict
 - ✓ Acknowledging the conflict and never ignore it
 - ✓ Stick to the facts and never get personal
 - ✓ Analyze the situation and encourage different perspective
 - ✓ Focus on a solution and never get stuck on things you can't do
 - ✓ Once you decide on a solution then move forward

Scenario: (Question: Second Question: On The First Project Day, The Team Divided Up Project Duties. Cynthia Designed The Robot Arm, Juan)

On day 1 of project, the team divided up project roles. Among the roles Cynthia designed the robot arm, while Juan designed the robot chassis, and Tri and also Robert worked on the computer programming, while Calvin volunteered to do the report writing and make the PowerPoint presentation.

On the day of testing, their robot still could not complete a specified reliable tasks and the group's oral report was disjointed and incomplete. What is the most likely cause?

- A. *A couple of people were not very smart, and they dragged the team down.*
- B. *The wrong people chose the wrong tasks.*
- C. *The members worked individually without much communication*
- D. *They didn't have a strong enough boss who could tell each person what to do*
- E. *They were not working hard enough*

Engineering Ethics

What is the engineering ethics?

(1) It is the study of moral issues and confronting individuals decisions and organizations involved in engineering.

(2) the study of related questions regarding moral conduct, character and peoples or organizations involved in technological development.

- **Engineering ethics**
 - Applied ethics
 - Focuses on a set of standards that cover engineers' responsibility to the public, clients, employers and profession
- **Engineering** – one of the fundamental human activities
 - Enormous social impact and significant responsibility
 - Engineers are often placed into conflict situations – they need to be able to resolve conflicts in an ethical manner.
- **Washington Accord/ABET** - acknowledged accreditor for colleges and university programs in engineering, computing, applied science, computing, and technology

- Requirement for teaching engineering ethics
- Goal – preparation of students for ethical challenges in technology dominated world

What are the purposes of the Code of Ethics for Engineers?

- Provide a right stimulus for ethical conduct
- Helpful advice about the engineers primary obligation of "engineers."
- Guideposts in interpreting ethical dilemmas

A society (i.e. engineering design team) grants certain privileges to individuals trained in engineering so that they apply their training to pursue satisfying and respected work. In return, engineers have professional responsibilities to various stakeholders within society engineers professional relationships with employers, clients, other engineers, and the general public;

These obligations include:

- honesty and competence in technical work,
- confidentiality of proprietary information,
- collegiality in mentoring and peer review,
- the welfare and public safety,
- Because the engineers' decisions can significantly affect society and the environment.

National Society of Professional Engineers (NSPE) (National Society of Professional Engineers)

Preamble NSPE Code of Ethics (National Society of Professional Engineers)

- Engineering is **learned profession**
- **that impacts society.**
- **Highest standards of honesty and integrity**
- of Engineers are expected by the society.
- The engineers services require **fairness, honesty, equity** and must be **dedicated to *protecting public health, safety, and welfare.***
- Engineers **performance** shall be in a **standard** of **professional behaviour** with adherence ***to the highest principles of ethical conduct***

General Rules (National Society of Professional Engineers)

1. Consider great importance on the safety and public welfare.
2. Perform services of competence.
3. Public statements issuance are truthfull and objective.
4. Anagent of employer or client as faithful agents or trustees.
5. Avoid deceptive acts.
6. Conduct themselves ethically and lawfully to enhance the profession's honour and usefulness.

Rules of Profession

*al Practice*_(National Society of Professional Engineers)

1. Engineers shall hold paramount the public's safety, health, and welfare

- a. Notify employer, client and other appropriate authority to overrule judgement if under circumstances endanger life or property,
- b. Approval of engineering documents by Engineers shall **conform to available standards.**
- c. Engineers **revelation of facts, data or information** without the client's or employer's prior consent except as authorized or as prescribed by law or this Code is a NO.
- d. Engineers **shall not allow their name or their associate** in any business ventures and with any individual or firm that they believe is engaged **in the dishonest enterprise.**
- e. Engineers **shall not aid or abet a person or firm's unlawful practice of engineering.**
- f. Engineers knowing any **alleged Code of ethics violation** shall **be reported to professional bodies** and cooperate with the proper authorities in providing such information or assistance as may be required.

2. The Engineers shall perform services only in the areas of their competence. (National Society of Professional Engineers)

- a. The Engineers shall **undertake assignments where their qualification** as to education or experience in the specific technical fields.
- b. The Engineers **shall not sign any plans or documents which the subject matter they lack competence** in, nor to any plan or document not prepared by them or under their direction and control.
- c. The Engineers may accept assignments, assume responsibility for the coordination of an entire project, seal and sign the engineering documents for the whole of the project, provided that ***technical documentation is signed and sealed by the qualified engineers only who prepared the technical documentation.***

3. The Engineers shall issue public statements only objectively and truthfully. (National Society of Professional Engineers)

- a. Engineers shall be truthful and objective in professional reports, testimony and statements. They shall include in the report all relevant and pertinent information, statements, or testimony, bearing the date indicating when it was current.
- b. Engineers may express publicly technical opinions based upon knowledge of the facts and the competence in the subject matter.
- c. The Engineers shall issue no statements, arguments, criticisms on inspired or paid for technical matters by interested parties. However, if they have prefaced their comments on whose behalf they are speaking by explicitly identifying the interested parties and by revealing the existence of any interested party may have in the matters.

4. The Engineers shall act as faithful agents or trustees for each employer or client.

(National Society of Professional Engineers)

- a. The Engineers shall **disclose all known or possible conflicts** of interest influencing or appearing **to influence the quality of their services** in their judgment.
- b. The Engineers shall not accept financial, compensation, or otherwise, for services on the same project from more than one party unless they fully disclosed the circumstances and all interested parties agreed to it.
- c. The Engineers shall not accept financial, solicit or other valuable consideration, directly or indirectly, outside agents connection with the work for which they are responsible.
- d. The Engineers who are members or employees of a governmental body or department in public service shall not participate in decisions, concerning solicited services or provided by them or their organizations in engineering practice private or public .
- e. The Engineers shall not accept a contract if their principal representative or officer serve as a member from a governmental body .

5. Engineers shall avoid deceptive acts. (National Society of Professional Engineers)

- a. The Engineers shall not falsify their qualifications, misrepresentation of their or their associates' qualifications. The Egnineer shall not exaggerate or misrepresent their responsibility in or for their subject matter of prior assignments. They shall not misrepresent pertinent facts about employers, employees, or past accomplishments in any other presentations brochures or incident to the solicitation of employment .
- b. The Engineers shall not offer, solicit or receive financial that influences on the award of a contract by public authority directly or indirectly, or that are construed by the public as having the effect of intent to influence the awarding of a contract. The Egnineer shall not offer any gift or other valuable consideration to secure work. the Egnineer shall not pay a commission, percentage, or brokerage fee to secure work.

Professional Obligations_(National Society of Professional Engineers)

1. The Engineers shall be guided by the highest standards of honesty and integrity in all their relations by .
2. The Engineers shall at all times uphold interest of the public.
3. The Engineers shall refrain all conduct or practice that deceives the public.
4. The Engineers without consent, shall not disclose confidential information concerning the technical processes or the business affairs or of any present or former employers.
5. The Engineers in their professional duties shall not be influenced by conflicting interests.
6. The Engineers to obtain employment or advancement shall not attempt to gain employment by criticizing other engineers untruthfully .
7. Engineers shall not falsely attempt to injure professional reputation of other engineers. The Engineers who believe others are guilty of unethical conduct shall notify to the proper authority for action.
8. The Engineers shall accept personal responsibility for their professional activities, where the Engineer's interests cannot otherwise be protected may seek indemnification for any services derived from their practice for other than gross negligence, .
9. The Engineers whom credit is due and to those to and will recognize the proprietary interests of others.

Are these actions right or wrong?

Case 1: (Mary discovers that her plant (factory) is discharging a substance into the river that the government does not regulate)

Mary discovers that her plant (factory) is discharging a substance into the river that the government does not regulate. She does some reading about the significance and finds that some studies shows it is a carcinogen. She believes she must protect the public as an engineer, but she also wants to be a loyal employee. The substance will probably be costly to remove, and her boss advises, "Forget about it until the government requires. Then all the other plants will have to spend money, and we will not be at a competitive disadvantage." ***What should Mary do?***

Case 2: (Tom is designing a new chemical plant. One of his responsibilities is to identify the valves to be used in a cer)

Tom is designing a new chemical plant and was invited by salesperson for one of the firms that manufacture valves or a golf game at the local country club before he makes the final decision before he makes the final decision. One of his responsibilities is identifying the valves used in a certain part of the plant. ***Should Tom accept the offer?***

Engineer's Australia Code of Ethics (Our Code of Ethics)

Under our accreditation, the Washington Accord, of which Engineer's Australia is a signatory, the guideline on the Code of Ethics is below:

The Guidelines on Professional Conduct provide a framework for members of Engineers Australia to use when exercising their judgment in the practice of engineering.

1

Demonstrate integrity

1.1 Act on the basis of a well-informed conscience

- be discerning and do what you think is right
- act impartially and objectively
- act appropriately, and in a professional manner, when you perceive something to be wrong
- give due weight to all legal, contractual and employment obligations

1.2 Be honest and trustworthy

- accept, as well as give, honest and fair criticism
- be prepared to explain your work and reasoning
- give proper credit to those to whom proper credit is due
- in managing perceived conflicts of interest, ensure that those conflicts are disclosed to relevant parties
- respect confidentiality obligations, express or implied
- do not engage in fraudulent, corrupt, or criminal conduct

1.3 Respect the dignity of all persons

- treat others with courtesy and without discrimination or harassment
- apply knowledge and skills without bias in respect of race, religion, gender, age, sexual orientation, marital or family status, national origin, or mental or physical handicaps

2

Practise competently

2.1 Maintain and develop knowledge and skills

- continue to develop relevant knowledge and expertise
- act in a careful and diligent manner
- seek peer review
- support the ongoing development of others

2.2 Represent areas of competence objectively

- practise within areas of competence
- neither falsify nor misrepresent qualifications, grades of membership, experience or prior responsibilities

2.3 Act on the basis of adequate knowledge

- practise in accordance with legal and statutory requirements, and with the commonly accepted standards of the day
- inform employers or clients if a task requires qualifications and experience outside your areas of competence

The Guidelines are not intended to be, nor should they be interpreted as, a full or exhaustive list of the situations and circumstances which may comprise compliance and non compliance with the Code of Ethics. If called upon to do so, members are expected to justify any departure from both the provisions and spirit of the Code.

Ethical engineering practice requires judgment, interpretation and balanced decision-making in context.

Engineers Australia recognises that, while our ethical values and principles are enduring, standards of acceptable conduct are not

permanently fixed. Community standards and the requirements and aspirations of engineering practice will develop and change over time. Within limits, what constitutes acceptable conduct may also depend on the nature of individual circumstances.

Allegations of non-compliance will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis and administered in accordance with Engineers Australia's General Regulations as amended by the Board from time to time.

3

Exercise leadership

3.1 Uphold the reputation and trustworthiness of the practice of engineering

- advocate and support the extension of ethical practice
- engage responsibly in public debate and deliberation

3.2 Support and encourage diversity

- select, and provide opportunities for, all engineering practitioners on the basis of merit
- promote diversity in engineering leadership

3.3 Communicate honestly and effectively, taking into account the reliance of others on engineering expertise

- provide clear and timely communications on issues such as engineering services, costs, outcomes and risks

4

Promote sustainability

4.1 Engage responsibly with the community and other stakeholders

- be sensitive to public concerns
- inform employers or clients of the likely consequences of proposed activities on the community and the environment
- promote the involvement of all stakeholders and the community in decisions and processes that may impact upon them and the environment

4.2 Practise engineering to foster the health, safety and wellbeing of the community and the environment

- incorporate social, cultural, health, safety, environmental and economic considerations into the engineering task

4.3 Balance the needs of the present with the needs of future generations

- in identifying sustainable outcomes consider all options in terms of their economic, environmental and social consequences
- aim to deliver outcomes that do not compromise the ability of future life to enjoy the same or better environment, health, wellbeing and safety as currently enjoyed

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